

CSH, ADHESION AND ANTI-BIOFILM STUDIES OF TPL AGNPS USING CENTRAL VENOUS CATHETER MODEL

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ABSTRACT

Candida albicans is a potent fungal microbe of humans which causes high horribleness and mortality in immune-compromised individuals. One more purpose for such bleakness is the set number of explicit medications accessible in the market for the avoidance of candidiasis. This study focuses on the potential use of *Thevetia peruviana* (Pers.) K. Schum. leaf extract (TPL) for the biosynthesis of silver nanoparticles (TPL AgNPs) exhibits inhibitory activity against *C. albicans*. TPL AgNPs inhibit biofilm and extracellular polysaccharide matrix formation on the surface of the catheter's lumen even at a low concentration. Therefore, attenuated biofilm development, morphogenic transformation, cell surface adhesion and cell surface hydrophobicity were observed. TPL AgNPs causes a decrease in Cell Surface Hydrophobicity, reduced adhesion at a concentration of 1.56 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ and hindered biofilm formation at 25 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. scanning electron microscopy (SEM), transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and X-ray diffraction (XRD) investigation confirmed the polycrystalline structure and round morphology of TPL AgNPs with 20 nm in diameter.

Keywords: *Candida albicans*, TPL AgNPs, Biofilm, Adhesion, Cell Surface Hydrophobicity.

I. INTRODUCTION

Adhesion, colonisation on firm surfaces and resulting biofilm development represent an incredible danger to the drawn-out utilisation of prosthetic materials and clinical gadgets, for example, cardiovascular catheters, endotracheal tubes and cerebrospinal liquid shunts [1-2]. The capacity to advance the change between yeast to hyphae morphology is one of the fundamental advances engaged with grip to various surfaces [3]. Cell surface hydrophobicity can elevate cell grip to multiple surfaces and aides in colonisation, biofilm arrangement and intrusion [4]. *C. albicans* is a significant reason for bleakness and mortality, most regularly saw in immune compromised patients [5]. *Candida* biofilm development assumes an imperative part in catheter contaminations, prompts the disappointment of clinical embedded gadgets, particularly central venous catheters, false teeth, and heart valves [6-8]. *C. albicans* positions fourth-most prominent reason for circulation system contamination which colonises cutaneous, gut, oral territories and present in the gastrointestinal plot of people [5,9-11]. *C. albicans* causes severe disease in a broad scope of host speciality because of its capacity for intrusion, filamentation, morphological progress, stress reaction and biofilm arrangement [12]. The contagious cell wall goes about as a protecting boundary that forestalls osmotic erupting from turgor pressure. The cell wall is fundamental for the development and expansion of organisms in a hypotonic domain. The cell mass of growths comprises β -glucans, chitin, manno proteins and various proteins. These are the constituents of cell wall which related to proteins to perform cross connecting and stretching [13]. A considerable lot of the polymers and wall get together proteins are fundamental for the creature and chemicals that integrate these constituents could be significant antifungal targets [14]. Even though different antifungal medications are accessible in the market, clinical confines are frequently safe. High medication portions might be compelling to forestall biofilm diseases yet may cause symptoms, [15-17]. Lately, nanotechnology becomes a significant device, particularly in industry, clinical sciences, material sciences, horticulture and ecological security and so on [18-21]. Old period silver is utilised as an anti-microbial operator against microbes, organisms and infections [7, 18, 22]. The preferred fundamental position of silver NPs (AgNPs) contrasted with drugs incorporates a high surface zone to volume proportion, which can undoubtedly collaborate with microorganisms in low portion focuses and non-harmful to mammalian cells [17, 23]. There are sure inadequately investigated as a worldview for novel antifungal medication disclosure [24]. Despite this,

fungicidal impacts of AgNPs has not yet totally clarified. Here, we investigated the cell wall collaboration with combined TPL AgNPs, which might be an essential procedure for hindrance and to focus on the layer uprightness of *C. albicans* is a vast arrangement to battle with micro-organisms. Focusing on layer honesty will be eye catching and perceive the instrument of hindrance activity by integrated TPL AgNPs. It could repress the yeast to hyphae progress, attachment, cell surface hydrophobicity and devastated extracellular polysaccharide grids to develop biofilms and furthermore constrict biofilm advancement on the outside biomedical gadgets, for example, central venous catheter at the low focus. This attenuation might be because of electrostatic collaborations and osmotic imbalance. Ag⁺ particles alongside *C. albicans* cell wall proteins initiate ROS creation prompting cell passing.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Synthesis and Characterization of TPL AgNPs

Thevetia peruviana (TPL) plant leaves were bubbled in the water at 70 °C for 15 minutes and separated through a Whatman's channel paper. AgNO₃ solution was acquired from Himedia Chemicals, Mumbai, India. The biogenic blend of the TPL AgNPs was synthesised from 1 mM AgNO₃ and leaf remove of *Thevetia peruviana* (TPL). Leaf separate of 3 mL was added to 1 mM 17 mL solution of silver nitrate and heated for 20 minutes at 50 °C. The adjustment saw this natural and biogenic amalgamation of TPL AgNPs in shading from light yellow to the dull earthy coloured colloidal arrangement [25]. Phytofabrication of TPL AgNPs was portrayed utilising a UV-vis spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV-vis Spectrophotometer) at the frequency of 200 to 800 nm with 0.5 nm scanning interval. Structural analysis for the functional groups presents in the biogenically synthesised TPL AgNPs was finished by Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) (8400 S, Shimadzu, Japan). To decide the gem grid and size of the TPL AgNPs, XRD estimation (XRD 6000; X-beam diffractometer), (Shimadzu; Kyoto, Japan) was used and from the half-width of central maxima size of the crystallite domain was calculated. The surface morphology, structure and size of blended TPL AgNPs were studied by a high-resolution TEM (Tecnaï G-2 F-20, FEI; USA) and SEM (S-3700N; Hitachi, Japan). To decide the net charge on TPL AGNPs, Zeta potential was estimated, (Photo Otsuka Electronics and Hirakata, Japan at 25 and 12 points)

2.2. Cultures, Culture Conditions, Media and Reagents

The strain ATCC90028 of *C. albicans* was acquired from the IMT, Chandigarh, Punjab, India and GMC3 strain of *C. albicans* was isolated from TB patient of GMC, Nanded, MS, India. For the preparation of inoculum and to sustain the culture, YPD is composed of 1% of yeast separate, 2% of peptone and 2% of dextrose, agar inclines at 4 °C and utilised for inoculum readiness. RPMI-1640 medium, 3-N-morpholine-propane sulfonic (MOPS), and 2,3-bis-(2- methoxy-4-nitro-sulfohenyl)-2H-tetrazolium-5-carboxanilide (XTT) were acquired from Himedia Chemicals, Mumbai, India. FBS (Fetal Bovine Serum), Menadione, Triton-X 100 was bought from Himedia Chemicals, Mumbai, India. From the YPD agar plate, a single colony was inoculated in YPD broth which is near about 50 mL of stock, and after that, it kept for incubation in shaking incubator (24 h and 120 rpm) at room temperature. Centrifugation of harvested cells from the initiated culture was done at 2000 rpm for 5 min and re-suspended in Sodium Phosphate Buffer of pH~ 7.4 after washing.

2.3. Evaluation of Planktonic Cell Growth

The planktonic cells growth impact with TPL AgNPs was evaluated by standard stock microdilution strategy dependent on Clinical Laboratory Standards Institute rules. TPL AgNPs concentration going from (0.78-100 µg mL⁻¹) were set up in the RPMI-1640 medium and transferred in non-treated plates (Costar; USA). To get 1×10³ cells mL⁻¹, RPMI and inoculums (100 µL) were then mixed in each well respectively. The absorbance was recorded at 620 nm to examine the growth using Microplate reader (Thermo Electron Corporation, USA) after the incubation period (at 35 °C, for 48 h). The least TPL AgNPs concentration at which there was a 5 half decrease in the absorbance contrasted with control was assumed as minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) for the development of *C. albicans* [26].

2.4. Minimum Fungicidal Concentration (MFC)

The MFC concentration of TPL AgNPs varies from (0.78-50 µg mL⁻¹), and the best was chosen. On YPD agar 10 µL of aliquots from wells were dissipated. Growth pattern from these plates was analysed after the incubation period (at 30 °C for 48 h). The fungicidal impact was seen due to the colony attenuation on agar plate [26]. The

microtiter well plate with minimum concentration of TPL AgNPs indicates no growth of colonies supposed as the MFC.

2.5. Hyphae Transition Assay

The impact of TPL AgNPs on serum-incited yeast to hyphal structure progress was explored in microtiter plate tests and concerning central venous catheter [27]. Different TPL AgNPs extending from 0.195 to 25 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ were set up in 20% of serum and Milli-Q water. Yeast was treated to acquire 1×10^6 cells mL^{-1} in both wells (test and control). These plates were incubated at 37 °C in a shaking incubator (200 rpm and 2 h). Cells were watched minutely for the shaping of germ tubes. The quantity of yeast cells to hyphae was counted out of 100 cells. The focus where indicated restraint of hyphae by $\geq$ half contrasted with the control was supposed as the MIC level for morphogenesis.

2.6. TEM

Morphogenesis developed at MIC of TPL AgNPs was observed after one and half an incubation hour under a light microscope. During the preparation process, centrifugation was done for tests (1500 rpm and 5 min) and the process of drying and fixation at 3000 rpm for 10 min for penetration in sterile conditions. After that, PBS of 0.05 M and 2% solution of glutaraldehyde were used to fix acquired pellet at surrounding temperature for 30 minutes. In following step, cells were cleaned thoroughly by the use of PBS. After that, they were fixed with 1% solution of OsO₄, at 4 °C for 2 h. In every step, the dried-out samples of ethanol series were kept in ethanol for 3 h and left for the time being in 100% Spurr's gum. In the following stage, pellets were set in coverslips which were recently covered with Teflon-like splash, and in 100% of Spurr's gum, it was "sandwiched" for the process of polymerisation for 24 h at 60 °C. In the wake of cooling, the resin which containing pellet was separated from the coverslips and observed in the stereoscopic magnifying microscope. The sectioning pellets were put in gum impedes and cut into pieces in an ultra-microtome machine (Leica Ultracut R). The small and thin segments near about 70 nm in size were mounted on a copper grid and used for dissected for TEM analysis (Hitachi H-7500 100 kV with a spot size of 5nm) [28].

2.7. Adhesion Assay

The microplate-based assay was utilised to study adherence properties of *C. albicans* and check the impact of TPL AgNPs to a massive surface such as the central venous catheter [29]. The PBS was used to synthesise TPL AgNPs with a concentration of 0.78-25 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. In control wells, there was no existence of TPL AgNPs and to acquire 1×10^7 cells mL^{-1} , 50 μl of suspension was added to each well. The 100 μl of concentration was kept as the final concentration for the assay. The plates were incubated in a shaking incubator (90 min and 37 °C) at 100 rpm to permit adherence of cells to the solid surfaces. The non-adhered cells were removed by PBS when the incubation time frame over. With the help of XTT assay, the thickness of the adherence was assessed for each well by RMA (relative metabolic action). If the decrease in RMA > 50%, its correlation with the control was significant.

2.8. CSH

CSH was previously reported by the various researchers in *C. albicans* [30]. All the experiments were acted in triplicate, and CSH was assessed by microbial attachment to the hydrocarbon. In short, cells were incubated and harvested, washed with PBS, and from the obtained yield optical density (OD) at 620 nm was observed. After that, in 3 test tubes of 1.3 mL, the cell suspension was disseminated, and 96 well plates 100 μl of cell suspension were added. Using ThermoScan-Ex microplate reader (Thermo electron corp-USA) absorbance was taken as an initial reading of cell suspension. After that, 0.3 mL of octane was blended with residual cell suspension (1.2 mL) in each test tube and segregate for 15 min. At that point, lower liquid phase was collected with a pipette and stacked 100 μl to the microtiter well, and final absorbance was taken at 620 nm. Test tubes without cells filled in served as control. The % of CSH was calculated by formula (%) CSH = (1-final O.D of fluid stage/initial cell suspension) X 100.

2.9. Biofilm Formation

In an in-vitro model, *C. albicans* form a biofilm on the outside of 96-well plates and the central venous catheter by forming a disc [29]. The cell suspension was inoculated from the stock (100 μl /well). The stock consists of 1×10^7 cells mL^{-1} , which were prepared in PBS. For adhesion, to solid surface, the plates were incubated in a

shaking incubator (120 rpm for 90 min). Therefore, this process allows for the removal of non-adhered cells. To allow biofilm formation, RPMI-1640 medium (200 μ l) was used. Varying concentrations of TPL AgNPs were prepared in RPMI-1640 and added in each well following the adhesion stage and kept for incubation. The action of TPL AgNPs was assessed against mature biofilm. After 48 h of incubation, the cells were analysed under Inverted Microscope to assess the presence of biofilm and photos were collected with a Labomed Microphotography System (Labomed; India) at $\times$ 100 amplification and the growth of biofilm development was inspected successfully.

2.10. Quantification of Biofilm (XTT assay)

Primarily XTT assay was performed to measure biofilm development [29]. To prepare XTT solution (1 mg mL⁻¹ salt) of XTT added in Milli-Q water and preserved in a -20 freeze. The final concentration (4 μ M XTT) was prepared along with menadione. Non-adherent cells were removed by PBS washing in the next step, and 100 μ l of XTT was added. Therefore, the wells containing biofilm were kept under incubation in a dim condition (37 °C and 5 h). The watery formazan product was estimated at a wavelength of 450 nm with the help of microplate reader. Absence of the TPL AgNPs was considered as control samples. TPL AgNPs concentration which caused $\geq$ half bringing down the metabolic (catabolic and anabolic) reaction, was supposed to be the MIC for the biofilm creation.

2.11. SEM

In 2.5% of glutaraldehyde formed in the PBS solution, biofilm developed on central venous catheters discs was fixed for a day at 4 °C and later on fixed in 2% of OsO₄ for 4 h. Ethanol dried samples were air-dried with a critical point dryer. In the next step, examine were sputter-coated with gold in the argon plasma at 11000 mA. An examining scanning electron microscopy (Hitachi; S3000N, Japan) pictures were recorded (high vacuum $\sim$ 10 kV) for knowing the structure of biofilm [31].

2.12. Cell Wall Protection Assay

This protocol was executed utilising the medium of RPMI [with and without sorbitol (control)] to assess conceivable instrument associated with the anti-microbial (antifungal) action of the test TPL AgNPs on yeast. Trials were done in triplicate to check the impact of TPL AgNPs in the proliferation of *C. albicans* and later on, MIC and MFC were assessed. After that 0.8 M sorbitol was included in the culture medium, this experiment was done in 96 well plates by microdilution and readings were measured on second and seventh days. As the sorbitol is a compound of osmotic stress condition, with sorbitol in the medium if the value of MIC is raised in correlation with the standard medium, it is supposed that the cell wall is a possible target for the product to be tested [32].

2.13. Growth, Viability and Kill-Curve Assay

The kill curve assay was studied according to the MFC standard strategy of M27-A3 by CLSI guidelines. MFC was viewed as the most minimal fixation for slaughtering 99.9% of cells. Kinetic energy for the counter candida act of silver NPs was concentrated by time-subordinate killcurve evaluation utilising *C. albicans* ATCC90028 and GMC3 strain [33].

2.14. Hemolytic Cytotoxicity Assay

The hemolytic exercises of the TPL AgNPs performed by utilising human RBC [33]. Human RBC's were collected from a fit individual, and 1–2 mg mL⁻¹ of EDTA was added into it as an anti-coagulant agent. In next step centrifugation of RBC was done at 634 $\times$ g for 10 min (Heraeus Megafuge-40) and the erythrocytes were separated (20 °C) and cleaned thrice in PBS. Once more, to get the yield of 10% (v/v) erythrocytes/PBS cell suspension, the PBS was added into the pellet. This suspension was diluted in 1:10 ratio with PBS, and 100 μ L of this suspension was added in each well to form a triplicate, and 100 μ L of TPL AgNPs were mixed in 1 mL Eppendorf tubes and 1% of Triton X-100 an essential agent was used for the completion of the reaction. The supernatant (150 μ L) was used in a level base microtiter plate (Tarsons Ltd. India) to measure the absorbance at 450 nm before this. The suspension was incubated for 1 h and transferred to conical bottom centrifuge tubes, and centrifugation was done for 10 min at 20 °C. Percent hemolysis was measured utilising the accompanying condition: Percent hemolysis = [(Abs (nm) of the mixture solution – Abs (nm) of PBS)/ (Abs (nm) of 0.1% Triton X-100 – Abs (nm) of saline)] $\times$ 100.

2.15. Statistical assessment

Figure showing the mean values to calculate standard deviation, which was acquired from unique perceptions. The numbers in the control and treatment bunches for different atoms were the outcomes of XTT were looked at utilising the Students t-test. An estimation of 'p' less than 0.05 was evaluated significantly [28].

III. RESULT

3.1 Characterization of TPL AgNPs

Reduction of $AgNO_3$ to Ag^+ with *Thevetia peruviana* leaves extract, form water-soluble TPL AgNPs. The colloidal solution of TPL AgNPs has an absorbance at 450-455 nm, which was confirmed by UV-vis spectroscopy (Fig. 1a). FTIR investigated the functional group of the blended TPL AgNPs. The FTIR range shows wide and solid groups at 3350 cm^{-1} , 1030 cm^{-1} and 2924 cm^{-1} (Fig. 1b), demonstrates the presence of aldehyde compound $H-C=O$ and 1624 cm^{-1} pinnacle shows hydroxyflavones and hydroxyxanthenes, 1750 cm^{-1} demonstrating the presence of $-CH-$ of alkane, 1425 cm^{-1} indicate the $-OH$ bend of polyphenol and an aromatic group carbonyl group. XRD analysis confirmed that obtained TPL AgNPs were pure Ag^+ monocline structure (Fig. 1c). All the noticeable peaks at two distinct positions 38.25° , 44.442° , 64.62° , 77.58° and 81.70° are listed too (1), (2 0), (2 0), (3 1) and (2) planes, suggest that the samples are translucent and have a cubic structure of silver (JCPDS # 87-0597). The cubic framework is met with the space group $Fm-3m$ which was determined unit cell boundaries ($a = b = c = 4.088\text{ \AA}$). The Bragg's pinnacles' 9 numerical computation was finished by estimating the molecule size from Debye Scherrer's equation. The normal crystallite size determined by the Debye-Scherrer condition, $D = (k \lambda) / \beta \cos \theta$ where 'D' is crystallite size, ' λ ' is X-beam frequency ($1.5406\text{ \AA}$), ' β ' is width, k is a regular ($k = 0.94$, accepting to be circular), full width at half most extreme (FWHM) for (311) and the diffraction point ' θ ' was $\sim 28\text{ nm}$. The zeta capability of TPL AgNPs is negative, which is -8.1 mV (Fig. 1d). The SEM and TEM pictures indicated that the readied TPL AgNPs was round and polydisperse with a normal size of $30\text{ nm} \pm 10\text{ nm}$ (Fig. 1 e-f).

Fig.1 a) UV-Vis spectra. b) FITR analysis c) X-ray diffraction patterns d) Zeta potential analysis. e) SEM f) TEM observation of TPL AgNPs.

3.2 Impact of TPL AgNPs on Different Virulence Factor of *C. albicans*

TPL AgNPs showed a base inhibitory impact on yeast after sequential attenuation with a beginning concentration of $0.78 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ on a microtiter plate. The TPL AgNPs indicated MIC and MFC of 12.5 to $25 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ respectively, while GMC3 strain demonstrated similar MIC and MFC values. GMC3 alone showed more extraordinary affectability when contrasted with standard ATCC90028 in rate (Fig. 2a, b-d and Table 1 & Table 2). We determined the effect of biosynthesised metallic TPL AgNPs on the most widely spread fungal microbe such as *C. albicans*.

Fig.2 a) Influence of TPL AgNPs on planktonic cell growth **b)** Maximum fungicidal concentration (MFC) **c)** Minimum inhibition concentration (MIC) of TPL AgNPs **d)** Control of *C.albicans* ATCC90028 strains.

The strains of *C. albicans*, i.e. ATCC90028 and GMC3 detached strains, were utilised to inhibit growth. Thus, TPL AgNPs treatment had a more susceptible effect on *C. albicans* hyphal formation, shown in TEM, and inverted light microscope (Fig. 3a and d-g) and Table 1). The impact of metallic TPL AgNPs on adhesion cells was determined at a low concentration which is $1.56 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for ATCC90028 and GMC3 strain (Fig. 3b). To evaluate the effect of TPL AgNPs on cell surface hydrophobicity over polystyrene 96 well plate and catheter of *C. albicans* strains, ATCC90028 and GMC3 were exposed to TPL AgNPs at MIC for 1 h before assay. The relative CSH was determined at $6.25 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of TPL AgNPs leads to 85% and 88% reduction of CSH for ATCC90028 and GMC3 strain. By specifying the % of CSH, it indicated an increase in CSH with cell adhesion and decrease in CSH with increased TPL Ag NPs concentration (Fig. 3c).

Fig.3 a) Yeast to hyphal transition of *C. albicans* ATCC90028 and GMC3 strains are treated by TPL AgNPs at different concentrations. **b)** Normal hyphal development of the fungal cells as adhering cells after one and half

hour of TPL AgNPs treatment as influencing adhesion cellular metabolic activity was determined by XTT assays of *C. albicans* ATCC90028 and GMC3 strains. c) Cell surface hydrophobicity of *C. albicans* strains ATCC90028 and GMC3 treated by TPL AgNPs.

Fig.3 Yeast to hyphal transition of *C. albicans* ATCC90028 strain are treated by TPL AgNPs was observed in light microscope as well transmission electron microscope with their cell wall destruction e), g) and control d), f).

We further studied their effect on biofilms formation by the metabolic growth assay, also called reduction assay (XTT). In reduction assay, XTT confirmed that TPL AgNPs significantly inhibited biofilm formation at low concentration, i.e. $25 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for both the strains in developing biofilm extracellular polysaccharide matrices of a mature biofilm (Fig. 4a and Table 1). The SEM and light microscopy observation of biofilm density depicted that significant reduction in biofilm formation after the treatment of TPL AgNPs (Fig. 4b) confirming that TPL AgNPs affect biofilm arrangement in *C. albicans*. In the below experiments, TPL AgNPs were used for further investigations such as demonstration of biofilm formation on the central venous catheter (model) with shaping plate described by a thick organisation of hyphal filamentous and yeast cell attenuated growth by TPL AgNPs (IC 99%) and $50 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of TPL AgNPs was directly used in SEM analysis (Fig. 4 c-d). Further, evaluate the possible mechanism engaged with the antifungal action of the test TPL AgNPs on the yeast cell wall by utilising sorbitol as a cell wall protectant. The impact was identified by the rise in MIC esteem for example $50 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, seen in the medium after sorbitol. The medium without sorbitol indicated a MIC estimation of $12.5 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for the two strains (ATCC90028 and GMC3) (Fig. 5a and Table 1 & Table 2).

Table.1 Comparison of MICs of silver nanoparticles (TPL AgNPs) against planktonic and biofilm growth of *C. albicans* ATCC90028 and *C. albicans* GMC3 strain.

<i>Candida albicans</i> strains		
MIC ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)		
Virulence factors	ATCC90028	GMC3
Planktonic growth	12.5	12.5
Sorbitol Stress	50	50
Morphogenesis	1.56	1.56
Adhesion	1.56	1.56

Biofilm development	25	25
Mature Biofilm	25	25
MFC ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)		
	25	25

Fig.4 Biofilm formations of *C. albicans* strains ATCC90028 and GMC3 treated by TPL AgNPs a) & b). The *C. albicans* cells were treated by TPTAgNPs- with different concentrations for 24 h and 48 h, and cellular metabolic activity was determined by XTT assay.

Fig.4 Normal growth and biofilm development of *C. albicans* treated by TPL AgNPs was observed by scanning electronic microscopy and simple microscopy. c), e) as control, and d), f) inhibitions of biofilm formation.

Fig.5 a) Influence of TPL AgNPs on cell wall sorbital content as a protection to planktonic cell growth. **b)** Killing of *C. albicans* colonies respect to time treated with TPL AgNPs on ATCC90028 and GMC3 strains **c)** Hemolytic activity of TPL AgNPs.

An increase in MIC values 10 demonstrated that the cell wall integrity was the major focus for the checked TPL AgNPs. After addition of sorbitol, *C. albicans* cells growth increased due to the protection mechanism. TPL AgNPs kill 100% cells of *C. albicans* for both the strains after 3 h and 1 h of incubation when exposed at MFC 25 µg mL⁻¹, but GMC3 strain is more sensitive to ATCC90028 strain (Fig. 5b). TPL AgNPs causes hemolysis of human RBC at various concentrations in a dose-dependent manner, 25 µg mL⁻¹ of concentration cause > 90% of hemolysis and 0.78 µg mL⁻¹ of concentration causes only 19.7% hemolysis (Fig. 5c).

IV. DISCUSSIONS

Biofilm formation of *C. albicans* among the immune compromised patient is an alarming situation for the increase in the occurrence of drug-resistant micro-organisms [9, 34-36]. Nano technological applications play an important role in inhibiting clinical pathogens and fascinate researchers with advantages such as lowered acute toxicity, less adverse effects, lowcost, eco-friendly nature and the capacity to defeat the opposition of micro-organisms [7]. The green union is considered a "base up approach" in which metal salts are decreased by the organic concentrate made of different proteins and optional metabolites with the conventional technique and eco-accommodating methodology [38]. *Thevetia peruviana* latex is notable for its antibacterial and antifungal properties [39]. Although several reports showed the strongest activity against the bacterial organism, fungi were less explored. Certain reports show that NPs influence virulence factors and biofilm formation of fungi [39-43]. Silver NPs' reaction with *C. albicans* cell membrane is associated with the electrostatic adhesion of attraction, which clarifies the inhibition mechanism. AgNPs are a novel and safe alternative to conventional antifungal agents at very low concentration with less adverse effect [28, 41]. NPs are known to cause cell membrane disruption [28, 45-46] ROS, [46] cell integrity [46] ion accumulation, [22, 28] and apoptosis, [24, 43, 47]. The several reports assessed that AgNPs are strongly acting as an anti-microbial agent on many pathogenic microbes, including bacteria (Gram-negative and Gram-positive) [22, 46-49]. This activity is attributed to specific properties of NPs for example; small size facilitates an increase in surface to volume ratio. There is charge compatibility between the membrane of microbes and the charged NPs [7, 24]. AgNPs induce surface membrane, and the distorted permeability of cell membrane leads to yeast's death [46]. In the cell membrane, proteins adhere to NPs of uniform size (20 nm) which is negative in charge can bind to the hyphae and yeast implies that they interact with cell adhesion proteins [43]. The NPs of uniform 20 nm - 40 nm size and negatively charged surface host been previously reported with bacterial cells, mammalian cells and

Saccharomyces cerevisiae [17, 50, 51]. Attachment to the surface film is the fundamental advance of biofilm arrangement, and cell membrane protein mediates the first association between micro-organism and surrounding environments [11, 52-55]. CSH is a kind of destructiveness factors can promote adhesion to the biotic and abiotic cell surface. Some reports indicate that CSH of *C. albicans* associated with surface colonisation and proliferates biofilm formations [4, 56-59]. Modification of the nearby environment may impact CSH, which retorts the host immune response; hence, adhesion is a virulence factor to a host surface that promotes infection by biofilms formation. Several reports suggest that antifungal drugs, i.e. ketoconazole, amphotericin B, 5-flucytosine, and fluconazole hindering pathogenicity by reducing CSH [55, 60-61]. Adhesion plays a crucial role in attachment on host surface or medical implanted devices with the help of ligand receptor-interceded attachment, for example, binding proteins which helps in the attachment such as laminin, fibronectin, fibrinogen and collagen along with manno proteins and agglutinin like sequence (ALS) [52-59]. Adhesion mechanism includes physical forces, for example, Vander Waals interactions, electrostatic associations and hydrophobic interactions [55, 58, 60, 62]. Cell wall constituents of *C. albicans* are liable for adherence to the surface which is surveyed the most vital stage while finding out disease, other than stress resilience, morphological exchanging, antigenicity, and other destructiveness connected cycles. The cell wall then improves large cell wall segments, for example, β -glucans, chitin, manno proteins, and other proteins associated with enzymes performing cross-linking, branching, and other functions. Hydrolytic enzymes which are secreted by *Candida spp.* Such as lipases, i.e. phospholipases, proteinases and hemolysin. These components may be one of the targets for cell destruction by antifungal agents; hence, sorbitol a stabiliser that helps cell survival in the medium [13, 63-65]. However, limited studies are available on interaction with NPs by using central venous catheters [67-69]. There are no reports available on cell surface hydrophobicity of *C. albicans* mechanism for targeting cell wall and cytoplasmic contents. In the present study, green-synthesised TPL AgNPs strongly inhibit virulence factors such as early biofilm formation, adhesion, CSH, hyphae transition in the central venous catheter as a model. However, for the first time, our study illustrates CSH, cell wall protecting assay and adhesion assay in a dose-dependent manner, demonstrated a substantial inhibitory impact on pathogenic biofilm development and intrusion to host cell. We explored the CSH interaction with silver NPs by suggesting that changes in the microenvironment may influence CSH, which retorts the host immune response, associated with adhesion, which is one of the virulence factors to host surface enhance infection by biofilms formation. CSH and adhesion process includes physical forces which also gives evidence about interactions of AgNPs. To assess the mechanism of the AgNPs against *C. albicans*, we studied sorbitol cell wall protection assay. It provides a unique insight into *C. albicans*, giving clues to understand the inhibition mechanism of synthesised TPL AgNPs. The experimental results from cell morphology and sorbitol protection assay imply that *C. albicans* combat with TPL AgNPs induced cell wall structure damage. The MIC was $12.5 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, which increased by threefold at $50 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of planktonic cells after adding sorbitol in RPMI medium. These broad changes promote osmotic pressure in the interior of *C. albicans*. This suggests that the nanosized (20 nm) with negative potential induces pores within the cell membrane, which leaks cytoplasmic content outside the cell. This action is related to the electrostatic communication among NPs and contagious fungal cell wall, consequently creating osmotic imbalance. Proteins consist of both the positive and the contrarily charged molecules. As a result, electrostatic fascination between TPL AgNPs and parasitic cell membrane intervened in their cooperation, which may be one of the possible targets for inhibitions. The evidence of the association between TPL AgNPs and *C. albicans* cell wall proteins could be associated with electrostatic attractions. Typically, *C. albicans* cell wall is thick, but treatment cell wall becomes thin (Fig. 3d and e). This shows that it might be due to formation of osmotic imbalance interior of the cell. This action is ascribed to unique properties of TPL AgNPs targeting cell wall protein, solid cationic attractions to the contrarily charged plasma film of micro-organisms, size-dependent induction and osmotic imbalance. Such properties lead to cell layer interruption, demolition of metabolism, and ROS generation, leading to cell death.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In our study following conclusions can be drawn.

1. CSH is associated step to promote adhesion and later contributes to infection by biofilm formation on the host surfaces. Interestingly, TPL AgNPs hindered the CSH of *C. albicans* cells associated with adhesion and biofilm formation.
2. TPL AgNPs shown a binding ability to the hyphae and cells of *C. albicans* and demonstrate adherence to the cell wall of *C. albicans*.
3. Cell wall protection assay and protein interactions confirm disintegration that leads to loss of essential cell constituents such as enzymes and functions associated with it give rise to cell death.
4. TPL AgNPs can analyze and treat *C. albicans* occurrence through CSH and adhesion to the hyphal cell wall at low concentrations.
5. TPL AgNPs can be used with polymers for central venous catheter production to resist or eradicate attacks of various micro-organisms in medical devices.

Therefore, novel properties of TPL AgNPs, which specifically inhibit CSH and provide evidence as a unique alternative to the antifungal drugs.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

All the authors declare no conflict of interest.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

IIT Bombay for providing the facility of TEM.

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